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Factors Enhancing Transborder Arms Smuggling and Insecurity in Idiroko-Igolo Border Communities, Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Ensuring proper border security in Nigeria and the Benin Republic has proven to be a formidable task for the authorities. One of the best indicators of a country's respect in the international community is its capacity to control entry and departure from its borders. Those who are within a country might be given an identity through border security. The study's goal was to investigate how security in border settlements between Idiroko and Igolo is affected by cross-border arms smuggling. This study used a qualitative research design. The sampling technique used in the study was a purposive sampling technique because it allowed us to select leaders of the border security management, community leaders, market leaders, and youth leaders on the basis of their depth of knowledge and experience on the issues under study. This necessitated the use of in-depth interviews in interviewing 20 respondents from border communities, 10 from each of Igolo, in the Benin Republic, and Idiroko, in Nigeria. The researchers manually transcribed the data and used thematic synthesis for analysis. The results indicated that the factors that enhance transborder arms smuggling in Igolo and Idiroko included the following: border porosity between Nigeria and the Benin Republic; inadequate intelligence gathering and sharing among border security organizations; corruption among some border security personnel; subterranean economic benefits linked to transborder arms smuggling; and a lack of participation from border community leaders in border management. The results also showed how the aforementioned elements compromise border community security, which fuels cross-border conflicts, the spread of weapons, and drug trafficking in Idiroko and Igolo. In order to improve intelligence collection and sharing between them and border security officials, it is advised that the governments of Nigeria and the Benin Republic immediately enlist the leaders of Idiroko and Igolo in border management.

Keywords: Border, Arms, Transborder Arms, Smuggling, Insecurity

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Factors Enhancing Transborder Arms Smuggling and Insecurity in Idiroko-Igolo Border Communities, Ogun State, Nigeria

Introduction

In security considerations, border protection is a major concern on a global scale. In addition to marking the boundaries of a country's territory or sovereignty, borders may bring both benefits and drawbacks to an economy, particularly for the border areas where the spread of illegal products and fluctuating currency rates cause problems. Because of their colonial past, the borders of developed countries are more secure than those in emerging countries, particularly those in Africa (Okereke, 2023). Ensuring sufficient border security in Nigeria has become a major concern for the administration. One of the best indicators of a country's esteem in the international community is its capacity to control entry and departure from its borders. Those who are within a country might be given an identity through border security. Nigeria's border security is seriously threatened by the fact that several of her borders are unmanned. According to Gbemre (2015), Nigeria has 84 legal borders and 1,497 illegal borders, with the majority of cross-border movement occurring through the illicit crossings. This implies that Nigeria's borders are porous, which may have played a significant role in the country's high degree of insecurity.

According to Adeola & Fayomi (2012), the existence of several unlawful borders between Nigeria and its near neighbours exacerbates the problem of illegal cross-border migration. The 932 kilometers that separate Nigeria and Niger are mostly porous or illegal boundaries. Nigeria and Chad share around 75 kilometres of borders, and to the south of the Atlantic Ocean, Nigeria and Cameroon share several unmanned land and marine boundaries. Hotspots for security are borderlands. This is

a result of how permeable borders affect border security.

The deterioration of our borders brought about by globalization and advancements in technology has made Nigeria more vulnerable to attacks, and this has jeopardized the country's security. The western border between Nigeria and Benin Republic is particularly well-known for a variety of illicit cross-border operations. Nigeria's insecurity problems necessitate a thorough examination of border entry sites to see whether they are fulfilling their strategic roles. Benin is home to thousands of Nigerians, whereas Nigeria is home to a smaller number of Beninese. However, in an effort to safeguard its borders, Nigeria has closed and reopened its border with Benin throughout the years, sending some Beninese back to their own country. The activities of some Nigerians, Beninese, and even citizens of other nationalities across the Idiroko-Igolo borders have been a constant threat to both countries' national security. These activities involve the smuggling of essential commodities like drugs and beverages, among other products, which may pose a security threat to Nigeria (Obaje, 2019).

The number and quality of weapons that former Niger Delta militants voluntarily turned in during the mobilization and disarmament phase of the Amnesty Programme in 2009, among them, 2,760 assorted guns, 18 gun-boats, 287, 445 ammunitions of various calibers, 1,090 dynamite caps, 763 dynamite sticks, 3,155 magazines, shows that the proliferation of weapons in Nigeria is problematic. Omilana (2020) also reported that approximately 10 million weapons are in circulation in the West

African subregion, with roughly 70% of these weapons being smuggled into Nigeria. Omilana further stated that non-state entities own more than 80% of the country's armaments. Consequently, the Nigerian Federal Government has taken a number of actions to address the issue of porous borders and how it affects the smuggling of products into and out of the country, particularly through the Idiroko-Igolo land borders. The issue of transborder arms smuggling and security in the Idiroko-Igolo border communities has persisted despite the implementation of many measures, such as combined border patrols, the arrest and prosecution of smugglers, the confiscation and sale of the smuggled goods, and the destruction of the smuggled goods, among others. Therefore, this study is geared towards the examination of the impact of trans-border smuggling of arms on security in Idiroko-Igolo border communities.

Literature Review

This sub-section of the study is comprised of a conceptual review and an empirical review. Conceptual review involved the review of the concepts of transborder arms smuggling and security, while empirical review involved the examination of previous studies on transborder crimes and security in Nigeria and Benin Republic.

Conceptual Review

Transborder Arms Smuggling

Before reviewing the concept of transborder arms smuggling, it is vital to review the concepts of border and arms. Numerous academics have defined borders in a variety of ways. According to Bellezza (2013), a state's territoriality and sovereignty are linked to the concept of a defined boundary. According to Belleza, borders provide countries with territoriality, which is crucial to understanding why sovereign states are required to protect international borders against unlawful cross-

border crossings. This is relevant to the study because it bolsters the contention that strong border security is necessary to prevent transnational criminals and smugglers from entering Nigeria, especially the land borders between Idiroko and Igolo. To understand the concept of border in this study, one must first understand how essential borders are economically, a subject that Bellezza's definition of border did not adequately address.

According to Norfolk & Hallgrimsdottir (2019), a border is a point of intersection or the line that separates two or more nations. These authors opined that a border can also serve as a point of admission or exit into a country. Some people think that borders might be utilized as a route for the smuggling of illicit goods and other transnational crimes since they act as points of entrance and exit for a country. However, Norfolk & Hallgrimsdottir's definition of a border did not address the need for border security, which is essential to maintaining Nigeria's security, particularly in border states where illegal entry into the country of arms and ammunition that can be used to commit crimes is possible. Furthermore, Okereke & Okoli (2020) filled in the previously mentioned definitional gap by emphasizing that the number of contraband items and other illegal products that are smuggled across borders would significantly decrease when a state's borders are sufficiently and properly guarded. This definition of border connects to the concept of border in this study because it suggests a potential relationship between border security and transboundary smuggling. However, the definition of border omitted the link between providing sufficient border security and diplomatic recognition to governments within the international community.

Borders are a constitutional means of limiting unauthorized border crossings into or out of a

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country (Eselebor & Kehinde, 2021). Eselebor & Kehinde went on to describe border as a crucial factor in determining whether or not a state is recognized in the comity of nations, provided that it is able to effectively defend its borders and, consequently, its population. It is crucial to comprehend the potential relationship between border security, diplomatic recognition, and a state's ability to keep its borders free from unauthorized entry, since this categorization of a state as strong, weak, or failed depends in large part on how well it keeps its borders secure. Nonetheless, the foregoing definition of border is slightly inadequate in this study because it did not extend to the need for frontier protection and safety of individuals in Nigeria, which are necessary in safeguarding the sovereignty of the country.

As seen above, a border is an officially recognized line of demarcation between two sovereign governments (the Republic of Benin and Nigeria), safeguarded by the two sharing the border in order to deter unauthorized border crossings. Communities that are bordered by borders benefit economically in many ways, particularly when their citizens take advantage of the enormous marketplaces and price differentials that exist there. However, borders also draw illicit activities, including trafficking, illegal commerce, hawking, and the smuggling of arms, which can have a detrimental effect on the security of border towns. Therefore, border communities, in this study, refer to Igolo and Idiroko settlements that are affected by arms smuggling between Nigeria and Benin Republic.

Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALWs) are the two categories of arms. Chilule (2014) described small arms as shoulder-controlled, man-made, portable weapons with a maximum length of 12.7 millimetres, or 0.5

inches. This group of weaponry has a level trajectory and an operating coverage that can range from 0 to 800 meters, depending on the weapon type and calibre. The fact that certain small weapons can deliver neutralizing firepower coverage of up to 1,800 meters supports this. In addition to providing useful examples of small guns, Chilule's definitions of small arms also define the capacity and number of people who can operate them, both of which are necessary for this study. However, the desire for and usage of weapons, which are equally important in this study, were not well addressed by Chilule, who came before them. In light of the aforementioned, small arms are defined in this study as human-portable, lethal weapons that may fire or launch explosives by easy reconstruction; small guns that are specified by domestic legislation or that were produced before 1899 are not included in this definition. Small arms are often easy for one person to operate and are intended for personal use.

Caleb (2019) clarified the descriptions above by mentioning that a single person may carry certain light weapons. Heavy machine guns, mounted and hand-held grenade launchers, and portable machine guns are examples of light weaponry. Nonetheless, it is important to note that the definitions of light weapons that have been considered thus far do not directly relate to security or instability. Considering the aforementioned, light weapons are described in this study as deadly weapons that are capable of being carried and used by two to ten persons who collaborate to commit crimes that result in the loss of lives and property. The paper's examples of light weapons correspond with those provided by Caleb (2019). This demonstrates how the spread of SALWs endangers people's lives and property, and that smuggling of weapons is one of the ways to make this happen.

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Smuggling has been characterized in a variety of ways by various academics in the body of existing literature. It is illegal to smuggle, and those who do so face penalties under the Customs and Excise Act and any other applicable legislation. The term "smuggling" refers to the unlawful importation, exportation, loading or unloading from a conveyance, as well as a diversion for the purpose of consuming goods subject to customs control with the goal of evading any applicable duties or laws or misleading the government (Guide for Importers and Dangers of Smuggling, 2023). The definition of smuggling given above clearly states that it is an illegal activity that violates customs laws, but it does not include the additional information required for this study, namely, that smuggling is an organized criminal activity in which other criminal gangs from various geographical locations throughout the world participate.

Horobets et al. (2020) claim that one of the risks to the state's border security, which is a crucial aspect of economic activity, is the smuggling of commodities. The unlawful transportation of commodities across the customs border with the intent to evade customs control is known as smuggling. Smuggling is differentiated by the following: weapons, plants, animals, artwork, software, copyright, and so on. One example of organized crime's expression is the smuggling of goods. While it is important to understand the potential connection between trans-border smuggling of goods and security in Nigeria, Horobets et al.'s definition of smuggling clearly states that it is an organized crime involving the movement of goods across borders in order to evade customs control. However, it does not explain the relationship between the importation and exportation of goods and security in Nigeria.

The unlawful import and export of commodities, typically done to avoid paying duty, is sometimes referred to as smuggling. Commonly, smuggling involves the selling of goods like illicit alcohol, cigarettes, or narcotics (Tax Disputes, 2023). The definition of smuggling given above includes the information required for this study, which is that smuggling, as an organized crime manifestation, often occurs during the importation or exportation of products. The impact of smuggling on security, which is crucial to comprehending the security implications for trans-border smuggling of products on security in Nigeria, required for this study, was not included in the description provided by Tax Disputes.

Heidari & Shafian (2015) added to the definition of smuggling by highlighting the various perspectives that may be used to interpret the term. Heidari & Shafian claim that smuggling might continue from unauthorized ports or places where customs authorities have no jurisdiction. This can also continue when items of all kinds, both permitted and unauthorized, are imported and exported across land, air, and maritime boundaries. Smuggling can also be carried out at authorized ports or continued with the assistance of customs officers; nevertheless, these scenarios did not fit our criteria for the definition of smuggling used in this study. Accordingly, the study defines smuggling as an organized criminal activity that involves the illicit transfer of both legal and illegal commodities via the land borders of Igolo and Idiroko in order to evade customs. The term "smuggling" refers to the trans-border smuggling of products between Nigeria and Benin across land boundaries, which might have a significant impact on Nigeria's security. Thus, the present study defines arms smuggling as an organized criminal enterprise that encompasses the unlawful transit of lethal weapons, capable of being carried and

controlled by 2 to 10 individuals who collaborate to commit crimes and function as a team to further criminal activities. This also covers deadly weapons that are human-portable and that may be used to fire or launch explosives by simple reconstruction; small guns that are specified by domestic law or that were produced before 1899 and cause property and human casualties are not included.

Insecurity

Before reviewing the concept of insecurity, it is vital to review the concept of security. Security can be defined from diverse perspectives because of its dynamic nature. Realist, idealist, constructivist, and securitization viewpoints are the main ones that contribute to the idea of security. Realists view security as the defense of a state's essential interests, particularly its territorial integrity and national sovereignty. Realists contend that, within the parameters of security and power, which are also gauged by a state's military prowess, security is concentrated on political and materialistic concerns. According to realists, security is the ability of a state to defend itself and its essential interests against outside threats, which is possible through military action. Constructivists describe security as a socially built phenomenon including interests, capacities, and dangers, whereas institutionalists define security as a combination of international collaboration and nation-building (Degaut, 2015). However, the foregoing did not establish the context-specific nature of security, which is also vital in this paper.

In addition, securitisation theorists adopt a contradictory viewpoint to the realists in their concept of security. Securitization theorists began by looking at the definition of security, which they consider to be a very contentious idea. Because security can have both positive

and negative qualities, researchers working under this theoretical framework contend that security depends on the situation (Eroukhmanoff, 2018). Security may be broken down into four sectors: political, military, environmental, and social. Each sector's referent object represents a particular danger. Akbar (2015) claims that the idealist viewpoint on security emerged in 1989 with the end of the Cold War. Idealists emphasize the individual as the primary referent object of security, in contrast to realists. The scope of security has grown to include, among other things, environmental, personal, health, and economic security due to idealists' stance on security. None of the definitions of security provided above linked it to the globalization wave, which is crucial to understanding the security threats posed by transborder arms smuggling and insecurity between Nigeria and the Benin Republic. Despite this, the definitions of security provided above offer us a variety of perspectives on the concept, which is essential to this study. Therefore, insecurity is defined as threats to the safety of residents of Idiroko and Igolo border communities, which further hamper the vital interests of Nigeria and Benin Republic.

Empirical Review of Previous Studies on Transborder Smuggling and Security between Nigeria and Benin Republic

Saka, et al. (2023) focused on information from the borders between the Nigerian and Benin Republics in their investigation of trans-border crimes and security issues related to regional integration in West Africa. The study's conclusions demonstrated how criminal activity along the borders between the Benin Republic and Nigeria affects both countries' national security and impedes efforts at regional integration. Although Saka et al.'s study examined trans-border crimes, which is relevant to the subject matter of this study, its conclusions did not address the

variables that influence trans-border armaments smuggling in the border settlements of Idiroko and Igolo and how they affect Nigerian security.

Blum (2014) analyzed cross-border movements between Nigeria and the Benin Republic by concentrating on the issues related to human security. The study's objectives were to illustrate the socioeconomic factors influencing the Nigeria-Benin border region and the intricacy of cross-border migration. The study's conclusions demonstrated that structural issues and underdevelopment throughout the continent are the root causes of transnational criminal activity in West Africa. However, these conclusions did not account for the factors that facilitate cross-border arms smuggling between Nigeria and the Benin Republic. The Benin-Nigeria border shutdown was examined by Abegunde & Fabiyi (2020), with a particular emphasis on how it would affect Nigeria's economic development. The study's conclusions demonstrated, among other things, that illicit commercial operations are evident along the Nigeria-Benin Republic border. These activities include the smuggling of illegal weapons and ammunition, illicit narcotics, diverted petroleum products, contraband items, and human trafficking. Nevertheless, the issues covered in this study were not covered by the findings.

To understand how trans-border crimes may be investigated, Fagge, Danguwa, and Muhammad (2021) looked at trans-border crime and its effects on Nigeria's national security and sustainable development. According to the study, transnational crimes seriously jeopardize Nigeria's good governance, political stability, social harmony, national security, and sustainable development. However, the study did not address the elements that facilitate cross-

border armament smuggling over the Idiroko-Igolo borders or the ways in which this may jeopardize Nigerian security.

Furthermore, Idris & Tutumlu (2021) used a whistleblower model to study trans-border management against guns trafficking in Nigeria and the Niger Republic. Results indicated that, on the Nigerian-Nigeria border, border communities were not included in the governance of border security, which created information asymmetry that favoured arms traffickers and seriously undermined the surveillance approach to border security management, a topic that is somewhat connected to this study.

Method

The design of this study was a descriptive research design involving qualitative research designs. This involved data collection from 20 respondents from border communities (10) from each of Igolo (Benin Republic) and Idiroko (Nigeria) using in-depth interviews. The participants in the interview involved leaders of the border security management community leaders, market leaders and youth leaders in the two border communities, comprising ten respondents from each of the Igolo and Idiroko border communities. The purposive interview technique was adopted in the study. This involved the selection of leaders of the border security management, community leaders, market leaders and youth leaders in Idiroko-Igolo border communities on the basis of their experience and depth of knowledge on issues related to transborder arms smuggling and insecurity in the study areas. Using a purposive sampling technique, 20 respondents were purposively selected, 10 respondents from each of the border communities. The sample size of 20 respondents is justified because the researchers expected that before 20 respondents are interviewed, the saturation point would have been attained and the

interview process discontinued. However, after the interview of 7 respondents, the researcher attained a saturation point and discontinued the interview.

The data collection process lasted for a period of one week. This period is justified because it enabled the researchers to identify the key individuals for the interview and engage them in discussion that led to either acceptance or rejection of some of the targeted participants. In carrying out the interview, the researchers used improvised sheets of paper and writing materials in jotting down the responses of the respondents. The researcher obtained the consent of the in-depth interview participants before the commencement of the interview. Nevertheless, all the respondents did not want their names mentioned or linked to their responses. In line with ethical considerations in research, we adhered to the requests of the interviewees.

However, the methodology adopted in this study has limitations associated with a small sample size. This is because a small sample size like the sample size of this study has the potential for biased or misleading results and difficulty in drawing precise conclusions about the bigger population. Data collected were manually transcribed by the researcher. This involved grouping similar responses irrespective of the participants who volunteered the views. The respondents were coded as in-depth participants 1 to 7 to avoid their names being mentioned. The data collected were analysed using thematic synthesis. This involved grouping the responses of the in-depth interview participants into themes and sub-themes until their views were adequately analysed.

Results

Results from the in-depth interviews were presented in themes and sub-themes as presented in Table 1.1 as follows:

Table 1.1: Thematic Table Showing Main Themes and Sub-Themes used in the Study

Theme 1	Knowledge of factors contributing to transborder arms smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo border communities
Theme 1, Sub-Theme 1	Key factors contributing to transborder arms smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo border communities
Theme 1, sub-theme 2	How factors enhancing transborder arms smuggling affect security in Idiroko-Igolo border communities

Source: Compiled by the Researcher (March 2025)

Table 1.1 shows that there was one major theme and two sub-themes in this study. The theme and sub-themes were used in the presentation of the findings as follows:

Theme 1: Knowledge of Factors Contributing to Transborder arms Smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo border Communities

Findings from in-depth interviews on knowledge of factors contributing to transborder arms smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo border communities showed that the majority of the respondents have in significant level of knowledge of factors that contribute to transborder arms smuggling between Nigeria and Benin Republic. Findings from in-depth interview participants 1, 3, 4, 6, and 7 on the foregoing showed that:

...many factors of different dimensions bring about an increase in arms smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo border communities. The factors are interwoven as a solution to one cannot mitigate border security challenges in the areas... the factors are known to the government and border security agencies...some of the factors are historical, while some are cultural, economic or even political... (Field survey, August 2024).

The foregoing findings showed that there are many factors that contribute to an increase in transborder arms smuggling between Nigeria and Benin Republic through Idiroko-Igolo border communities. Findings also showed that the majority of the in-depth interview participants are knowledgeable about the factors that compromise border security in the study areas. However, in-depth interview participants 2 and 5 noted that:

...the border security agencies are aware of the factors...they are not doing anything tangible to mitigate the factors...the factors can be mitigated if the security agencies between the two border sides cooperate in intelligence gathering and sharing... some community leaders and residents of border communities are facilitating transborder arms smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo border communities (Field survey, August 2024).

Responses from in-depth interview participants 2 and 5 showed that the factors contributing to transborder arms smuggling need an adequate and sincere approach by border security agencies in order to mitigate it. The implication of the finding is that transborder cooperations among border security agencies and relevant stakeholders in the border communities are needed to mitigate factors that enhance transborder arms smuggling between Nigeria and Benin Republic.

Theme 1, Sub-Theme 1: Factors that Enhance Transborder Arms Smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo Border Communities

Findings on the impact of transborder arms smuggling on security in Idiroko-Igolo border communities from in-depth interview participants 1 to 7 showed that:

...factors enhancing transborder arms smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo border communities are poverty, border porosity, corruption among some border security personnel, lack of adequate information sharing among border security agencies in the borders, connivance between transborder

arms smugglers and some residents of border communities, lack of adequate use of surveillance gadgets in tracking and arresting transborder criminals in the borders...underground economic benefits derivable from the crime motivate some youths from the border communities to indulge in the crime...abandonment of border communities by the government in the area of infrastructural development...(Field survey, August 2024).

Findings from theme 1, sub-theme 1, show that there are many factors of diverse dimensions enhancing transborder arms smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo border communities between Nigeria and Benin Republic. The factors range from institutional factors, societal factors and individual factors. The finding implies that transborder arms smuggling in Idiroko and Igolo borders is a transnational crime that is caused by a multiplicity of factors. This further shows that a multidimensional approach is needed in combating transborder arms smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo communities.

Theme 1, Sub Theme 2: How Factors Enhancing Transborder Arms Smuggling Affect Security in Idiroko-Igolo Border Communities

Findings from in-depth interviews with participants 1 to 7 on how factors enhancing transborder arms smuggling affect security in Idiroko-Igolo border communities show that:

...huge proceeds from transborder arms smuggling encourage more unemployed residents of the border communities to indulge in the crime and this increase the number of people illegally crossing the borders with illicit arms... inadequate border protection and lack of political will embolden arms smugglers to smuggle more arms through the borders... corruption among the border security personnel and lack of adequate intelligence gathering and sharing increase the number of arms successfully smuggled into the country through Idiroko and Igolo borders... poverty and desire to amass wealth

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within a small space of time encourages more residents of the border communities to connive with transborder criminals in concealing illicit arms in the border communities... (Field survey, August 2024).

The finding implies that the more the factors that enhance transborder arms trafficking are allowed to fester, the more the Idiroko-Igolo border communities are compromised. This affects not only the security of the border communities, but may increase the level of arms and ammunition in circulation and available to non-state actors such as terrorist and insurgent groups. With the increase in the activities of armed non-state actors, the more the level of global security is threatened.

Findings from the in-depth interview with participants 2, 3, 4, and 7 further show that:

...some residents of the border communities believe that arms smuggling contributes to the economic wellbeing of the border communities....arms traffickers lodge in motels in the border communities... patronise bars, restaurants and similar businesses in the border communities, which contribute to the economic wellbeing of the border communities... arms smugglers clash with border security agencies leading to killings...some residents eat from proceeds of arms smuggling... neglect of border communities make some of the residents of border communities connive with transborder criminal gangs in perpetuating arms smuggling by providing them safe havens in their communities...for the beneficiaries, the business is good and any attempt to disturb the business is seen as threat to their economic wellbeing... (Field survey, August 2024).

In-depth interview participant 6 examined the human security factors that enhance arms smuggling through the borders between Nigeria and Benin Republic. The responses showed that:

...lack of adequate number of primary and secondary schools in the border communities breed illiteracy, which increases the level of

poverty in the border communities, hence impacting adversely on security in the border communities..., absence of tertiary institutions, and absence of medical centers make some of the residents of border communities participate in smuggling (Field survey, August 2024).

From the foregoing, the majority of the respondents believe that the activities of transborder arms traffickers have underground economic benefits, which may help in the sustenance of some of the residents of the border communities. The implication for this finding is that residents of Idiroko-Igolo border communities may work with trans-border criminal gangs in one way or the other to encourage the illicit enterprise. This could further increase cross-border threats, not only in the border areas, but also in the border communities and beyond.

The implications for the foregoing findings are that the relative ease with which trans-border criminals Idiroko-Igolo land borders into Nigeria could be responsible for the increase in the level of transborder attacks by criminal gangs being experienced in Idiroko border community. This further shows that transborder arms smuggling in Igolo-Idiroko borders is responsible for increased collaboration between arms smugglers and other trans-border criminal gangs in perpetuating the proliferation of Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALWs), starting with the border communities, and later to the country as a whole. This increases the spate of terrorism and violence in the country given that the crime may lead to influx of criminal elements from other countries who would connive with their counterparts in Idiroko and Igolo in inflicting harm on the residents of border communities between Nigeria and Benin Republic, especially when the residents and border security personnel are opposed to their activities.

Discussions

The findings of this study indicate that factors such as corruption, lack of political will, border porosity, lack of adequate intelligence gathering and sharing among border security agencies, lack of adequate use of surveillance gadgets facilitate transborder arms smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo border communities, which further lead to compromise of border security in the areas. With systemic corruption in Nigeria, some border security personnel sometimes connive with the transborder criminal gangs and some residents of border communities in facilitating transborder arms smuggling through Idiroko-Igolo borders. With the increase in the level of corruption among some border security agencies in both the Nigeria and Benin Republic sides of the borders, some of the border security personnel may conceal intelligence or even share it with some transborder criminal gangs, thereby not only enhancing illicit transborder movements by transnational criminal actors, but also hampering the safety of life and properties of the residents of the border communities. The foregoing is supported by findings from Saka, et. al. (2023) and Fagge et. al. (2021), which showed transborder criminal activities between Nigeria and Benin Republic hamper the national security of both countries. This is linked to the findings of this study, given that transborder arms trafficking between the two countries leads to an increase in the volume of arms and ammunition in circulation in the country, given the ease with which transborder criminals cross the Idiroko-Igolo land borders, sometimes with the connivance of some border security personnel. With the increase in the volume of illicit arms available to non-state actors in the border communities, transborder attacks in the border communities have increased, sometimes leading to killings and destruction of properties. Also, findings by Abegunde & Fabiyi (2020) showed that transborder arms smuggling and related

criminal activities take place in shared borders between Nigeria and Benin Republic, which may be linked to the numerous factors that enhance the crime between the two countries such as porous borders, corruption, lack of political will and lack of adequate intelligence gathering and sharing among border security agencies in Idiroko-Igolo borders. Nevertheless, the findings by Saka, et. al. and Fagge et. al. did not cover the factors contributing to arms smuggling like the findings of this study.

Regarding how factors enhancing transborder arms smuggling affect security in Idiroko-Igolo border communities, the findings of this study showed that arms smuggling contributes to the economic well-being of some of the residents of Idiroko-Igolo border communities. This is because when arms smugglers lodge in motels in the border communities, patronise bars, restaurants and similar businesses, they contribute to the economic well-being of the border communities. This is because of the increase in the level of human security threats in the border communities, such as poverty, neglect of border communities in terms of infrastructural development, among others. The neglect of border communities makes some of the residents of border communities connive with transborder criminal gangs in perpetrating arms smuggling by providing them safe havens in their communities. Also, for the beneficiaries, arms smuggling is their source of livelihood, and any attack on the business is perceived as a threat to their economic well-being. With the foregoing, the level of arms smuggling in Idiroko-Igolo communities would continue to fester. The finding by Blum (2014) linked transborder criminal activities to underdevelopment in West Africa, which is related to issues of neglect of border communities, poverty, illiteracy, among other human security challenges identified in this study.

Nevertheless, the finding by Blum did not cover Idiroko and Igolo border communities. Also, findings by Idris & Tumumlu (2021) showed that border communities between Nigeria and Benin Republic are excluded from border governance, which hampers intelligence gathering and intelligence sharing on security threats in the areas. Therefore, the findings by Idris & Tumumlu largely support the findings of this study.

Conclusion

This study investigated the factors enhancing transborder arms trafficking and insecurity in Idiroko and Igolo border communities. The findings of this study largely contributed to addressing the gaps identified in previous studies on transborder crimes and security between Nigeria and Benin Republic by identifying how many factors, including lack of adequate intelligence gathering and sharing among border security organisations, corruption among some border security personnel, border porosity between Nigeria and Benin Republic, underground economic benefits associated with transborder arms smuggling, lack of involvement of border community leaders in border management, among others, hamper border security in Idiroko-Igolo border communities. Findings of this study linked factors enhancing transborder arms smuggling and insecurity in Idiroko-Igolo border communities to an increase in transborder clashes, arms proliferation, and drug trafficking in Idiroko and Igolo, which were not covered in the previous studies. In view of the foregoing, it is concluded that unless the Government of both countries mitigate the factors enhancing transborder arms smuggling in Igolo and Idiroko border communities, transborder insecurity would continue to rear its ugly heads in border communities between Nigeria and Benin Republic as well as in countries that share borders with the two countries.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The Governments of Nigeria and Benin Republic should establish joint intelligence sharing platforms between Nigeria and Benin Republic;
- ii. The Governments of the two countries should purchase and deploy surveillance equipment in Idiroko-Igolo borders with a view to monitoring and tracking illicit movements across the borders;
- iii. The governments of Nigeria and Benin Republic should curb the challenge of corruption among border security operatives by increasing their allowances and activating the policy of whistleblowing aimed at discouraging increasing incidences of connivance between transborder criminal gangs and some border security personnel facilitating transborder arms smuggling through their shared borders.
- iv. The government should sensitise the residents of border communities through the National Orientation Agency to enlighten them on the dangers of arms smuggling through their communities. This is aimed at discouraging some of them from conniving with transborder arms smugglers in perpetuating the crime.
- v. Lastly, the Governments of Nigeria and Benin Republic should also deploy drones to monitor the borderlines between the two countries to check illicit transborder crossings by arms smugglers and other transborder criminal gangs.

References

Abegunde, O. & Fabiyi, R. (2020). Nigeria Benin border closure: Implications for

- economic development in Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science Studies (JHSS)*, 2(4), 56-65.
- Adeola, G. & Fayomi, O. (2012). The Political and security implications of cross-border migration between Nigeria and her Francophone neighbours. *International Journal of Social Science Tomorrow*, 1(3), 1-9.
- Bellazza, G. (2013). *On borders: from ancient to the postmodern times*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/269782217>
- Blum, C. (2014). *Cross-border flows between Nigeria and Benin: what are the challenges for (human) security?* Retrieved from <https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/business/Nigeria/>
- Caleb, L. (2019). *Implementation of the ECOWAS convention on the proliferation of small arms and light weapons in Nigeria, 2009 -2017*. A Doctorate Degree Thesis Submitted to the Department of Political Science, Nasarawa State University, Keffi.
- Chelule, E (2014). Proliferation of Small Arms and Light Weapons: Challenge to development, peace and security in Africa. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)* 19, (5) 80-87.
- Degaut, M. (2015). *What is security?* Retrieved from <https://researchgate.net/publication/>
- Eroukhamanoff, C. (2018). *Securitization theory: An introduction*. Retrieved from <https://e-ir.info/2018/01/14/securitisation-theory-an-introduction>
- Eselebor, W. & Kehinde, O. (2021). *Border management and Nigeria's national security*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/>
- Fagge, M., Danguguwa, K., & Muhammed, Y. (2021). Trans-border crime and its implications on Nigeria's national security and sustainable development. *African Scholar Journal of African Sustainable Development*, 21(2), 173-188.
- Gbemre, Z. (2015). The need to protect the integrity of Nigerian borders. Retrieved from <http://reformonline.com/the-need-to>
- Guide for importers and Dangers of Smuggling. (2023) *Smuggling*. Retrieved from <https://www.mra.mw/asserts/uploads/guide-for-importers-and-smugglingbrochure.pdf>
- Heidari, H. & Shafian, A. (2015). Factors affecting goods and currency smuggling in the draft bill to combat goods and currency smuggling. *European Online Journal of National and Social Sciences*, 4(2), 316-322.
- Horobets, N., Reznik, O., Tkachenko, V. & Belanuk, M. (2020). Smuggling of goods as a strategic threat to the economic security of European states. *REICE Revista Electronica de Investigacion en Ciencias Economicas*, 8(15), 346-357
- Idris, A. & Tutumlu, A. (2021). *Nigeria and Niger Republic trans-border management against arms trafficking: a whistleblowing model*. Retrieved from <https://www.academis.edu/654408888888888840/nigeria->

- Norfolk, A. & Hallgrimsdottir, H. (2014). Sex trafficking at the border: An exploration of anti- trafficking efforts in the Pacific Northwest. *Journal of Social Science*, 8(115), 1-18.
- Obaje, A. (2019). *Transnational arms threats and national security in Nigeria*. A Dissertation Submitted to the School of Postgraduate Studies, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, for the Award of Degree of Masters of Science in Political Science (International Relations)
- Okereke, E. & Okoli, U. (2020). Cross-border human trafficking and its implications on border security of Nfem, Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Publications (IJORP)*, 4(4), 122-136.
- Okereke, E. (2023). *Impact of cross-border human trafficking through Seme-Idiroko borders on security of Lagos and Ogun States*. A Paper Submitted to the Department of Political Science, Nasarawa State University, Keffi in Partial Fulfillment for the award of PhD in Political Science (International Relations).
- Omilana, T. (2020). *How proliferation of small arms is enhancing violence in Nigeria- Report*. Retrieved from <https://www.guardian.ng.com/report/>
- Saka, L., Bakare, A., Nwaorgu, H., & Oladejo, S. (2023). *Transborder crimes and the challenges of regional integration in West Africa: Insights from the Nigeria-Benin Republic borders*. retrieved from <https://revista.unap.ro/index.php/>